

MONUMENTS OF ANCIENT KHOREZM**Ismailov Tokhirjon Khushnudbek ugli**

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Tuproqqala - the treasure of ancient Khorezm or the city of Earth - is one of the most valuable and majestic monuments of ancient Khorezm. Tuproqqala (I-VI centuries AD) is located a few kilometers south of the Sultan Uwais mountain range. This castle served as the residence of the rulers of Ancient Khorezm in ancient times, before the Afrigid dynasty came to power. This monument, like many other monuments of the ancient Khorezm civilization, was discovered by the famous archaeologist and historian Sergey Pavlovich Tolstov. These searches took place in 1938. The area of the city is 120 hectares, and it was later revealed that there was once a city surrounded by a defensive wall and square towers and a luxurious castle-palace. The name of the monument, based on its current position, means a large earthen mound.

Tuproqqala complex consists of the city, the upper palace and the northern complex. City - area 500 × 350 m. It is rectangular in shape and surrounded by defense walls 8-9 meters high. In addition, the city has many rectangular towers with flat corners, and the sides are surrounded by a wide moat. The city gate was built in the form of a complex structure, and a central street with a width of 9 meters passed through the city from this gate to the castle.

Once upon a time, the magnificent castle was the core of the ancient city and was the residence of Khorezm kings in II-III centuries AD. Here, behind the defensive wall, there were galleries protecting against enemy attacks, many streets and stalls were located, and there was also a wide front street in the center. The ancient city was so big that its territory included 10 quarters with about 200 farm and residential buildings. Each quarter has its own small centers, where shrines and craft buildings are located. More than 2.5 thousand inhabitants lived in the city, half of them worked in the palace residence.

The main part of the palace is occupied by a complex of prayer and ritual rooms. The walls of the building are decorated with patterns, and the five halls belonging to it are decorated with colorful ceramic bas-reliefs. Few of these ornaments have survived.

The castle consisted of three floors. Many relics were found in its rooms: remains of food (bones, seeds), pieces and whole parts of dishes, various dishes, jewelry, statues (one of the most famous statues is the statue of the Priest), paintings and even ancient Khorezm manuscripts.

In the center of the luxurious palace was a throne room decorated with magnificent wall paintings and antique patterns. In the "Hall of Kings" statues of Hellenistic art, various portraits and statues with very realistic faces were found. Excavations of the Tuproqgala caused a stir, and the fact that the city was the advanced capital of Ancient Khorezm in the 3rd century, the ancient culture flourished on this land, the streets and buildings were well designed, and the Turqqala could be called the kingdom of geometry. interesting materials were obtained that allow us to draw conclusions about.

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